

Plan of the Dissemination and Communication activities -1st version/D7.2

WP 7, T 7.2

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1 Technical references

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3 Executive summary

The Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Plan outlines an effective approach to promoting RECONSTRUCT's results while ensuring maximum impact. The plan includes communication and dissemination activities in the light of a preliminary list of Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and the identified key stakeholder groups. Then, it creates targeted key messages and the related dissemination tools and channels. The plan also clarifies the monitoring activities to evaluate the project's impact on the target audience and ensure maximum content outreach and engagement.

The document is structured as follows:

Chapter 2: This section explains the RECONSTRUCT integrated approach to communication, dissemination, and exploitation, highlighting the project's main goals.

Chapter 3: This chapter focuses on communication and dissemination, activities. First, it identifies RECONSTRUCT's Key Exploitable Results (KERs), the preliminary key stakeholder groups that can help maximize the project's impact.

Later, it outlines the key messages and communication channels and formats that will be utilized to spread information related to the project and promote its results. The chapter also describes how the communication and dissemination activities will be managed by the local D&C desks.

It also explains the monitoring processes and methodology developed by ICONS, which will be used to evaluate the audience's engagement with the communication materials. The chapter ends by discussing the impacts of the dissemination and communication activities, along with the indicators that will be used to measure them.

Chapter 4: a summary of the previous chapters is provided, and the chapter draws some preliminary conclusions, remarking that the current strategy will be subject to future revisions in the Plan of the Dissemination and Communication activities - 2nd version (M24).

This document is based on the general description of WP7, related to communication and dissemination activities. It will be updated during the project's implementation.¹

Table 1: Communication and Dissemination activities

Activity	Timing	KPI DoA
Visual identity	M2	-
Power Point and Word templates	M2	-
Landing page	M2	-
Social media channels (LinkedIn and Twitter ¹)	M2	>800 followers in total
Website	M6	-
Communication Kit (leaflet, roll-up, video)	M8	>500 downloads >500 copies distributed

¹ Despite Twitter is now X, it will still be called Twitter throughout the document.

Info-Packs	Throughout the project's duration	>1 per target group
Scientific Publications	Throughout the project's duration	>8 articles published on top rank peer-reviewed journals
Conference proceedings	Throughout the project's duration	>8 conferences attended >3 poster presentations
e-Newsletter	6-month frequency	>8 issues
Policy Briefs	Throughout the project's duration	>1 policy brief >2 presentations held at relevant EU premises
Press Releases	Throughout the project's duration	>8
Journalistic Articles	Throughout the project's duration	>2
Videos (including video-interviews)	Throughout the project's duration	>400 views in total
Social Media Campaigns	1 per year	>1 social media campaign organized per year of project implementation.
Joint events	Throughout the project's duration	>3 joint events organised
Organisation of webinars and workshops	Throughout the project's duration	>4 workshops/webinars organized in conjunction with big sectorial events
Open Labs at Demo Sites	Throughout the project's duration	>3 open labs organized in each demo-site (Brussels and Barcelona)
Innovation Handbook	End of project	1
Final Event	End of project	1

4 Introduction: an integrated approach to dissemination, exploitation, and communication

4.1 Introduction

The construction sector in Europe has a significant impact on the environment. The RECONSTRUCT project, funded by the EU, aims to achieve greater circularity, and reduce this impact. To achieve this, the project will develop low-carbon alternatives to cement and steel. The project will focus in particular on manufacturing construction components that use recycled materials and are designed for modularity. In addition, it will focus on embedding deconstruction in building design.

The circular approach will be implemented through digitization and regionalization of the construction value chain. The project's impact potential and economic feasibility will be demonstrated through real-scale pilot buildings in Brussels and Barcelona.

To achieve this objective, it is imperative to formulate and oversee an effective strategy for communication, dissemination, and exploitation. This strategy should be tailored to the outcomes that aimed to be promote and the specific target audience that the project is addressing.

Starting from the project's initiation and spanning across WP7, actions related to dissemination, communication, and exploitation are set in motion to identify and engage the most relevant stakeholders within the scope of RECONSTRUCT, including potential end-users, public authorities, and other key participants.

The activities pertaining to Dissemination (D), Exploitation (E), and Communication (C) will be intricately interwoven and executed in a coordinated manner to achieve the following objectives:

- Enhance project visibility and provide information about the project's benefits and impacts to target audiences and wider communities (C).
- Share knowledge and engage key players, facilitators, and early adopters through a tailored and specialized strategy (D).
- Establish a pathway for the utilization of RECONSTRUCT's outcomes (E).

The RECONSTRUCT "Plan of Dissemination and Communication activities - 1st version" adopts a comprehensive and impact-driven approach with the objective of creating impacts in three key areas: i) raising awareness and understanding, ii) fostering the acceptance of innovation, and iii) promoting the adoption and expansion of the project's outcomes even after the project concludes.

To elaborate further, the plan is founded upon the identification of critical key exploitable results (KERs) and relevant stakeholders. This analysis serves as the basis for crafting focused and direct actions (comprising messages, content, channels, tools, and engagement activities) at various geographical levels over time. The implementation of an effective dissemination, exploitation, and communication strategy will not only facilitate stakeholder adoption of the project's outcomes but also contribute to ongoing advancements beyond the project's lifespan.

A continuous evaluation of the strategy's impacts and effectiveness will be carried out using a specialized methodology developed by ICONS. This methodology relies on a range of indicators and indices, including the Community Engagement Index (CEI), which assesses the active participation of stakeholders in the project. Ongoing monitoring activities will offer consistent feedback to the Project Execution and Development Team (PEDR), enabling them to make refinements and improvements at various project stages.

4.2 Objectives and approach to dissemination, communication, and exploitation

The aim of WP7 is to engage with RECONSTRUCT's key stakeholders and increase awareness, acceptance, and adoption of project outcomes in Europe through effective communication and outreach actions.

This exercise will start with the analysis of the needs addressed by RECONSTRUCT and its expected outcomes:

Table 2: Specific needs and expected results

SPECIFIC NEEDS	EXPECTED RESULTS
Recycling rates of CDW are high but the majority is downcycled and a small fraction is used in buildings.	Construction materials with minimum virgin content and very low carbon footprint (AAC, AACC, TRRC).
There is currently no green alternative to OPC that is scalable and technically/economically competitive.	Modular construction components designed for disassembly and reuse.
The formation of resilient supply chains of secondary resources and waste is a prerequisite for circularity.	Construction method for zero waste generation and deconstruction method for 100% material recovery.
Onsite construction is still the dominant construction method and wastes approx. 15% of building material.	Digital ecosystem for the sourcing of CDW and identification of cross sectoral industrial symbiosis.

Circularity is hampered by the lack of digitization in the value chain to track and share info on materials.	Digital twin of buildings based on a dynamic 6 D-BIM with simulation and generative design capabilities.
Despite the extensive use of BIMs they are still used as static representations without forecasting capabilities.	Blockchain-based system for tracking, tracing and sharing info on construction materials and components.
The construction industry is commercially organized as a linear industry and lacks circular business models.	Two real-scale buildings demonstrating the impact of the aforementioned solutions in real environment.
The perceptions and acceptance of circularity by construction stakeholders is unknown.	Circular Construction Framework packaging lessons, policies, & business models in replicable form.

In particular, the RECONSTRUCT Plan for Dissemination and Communication activities is intended to:

1. Continuously and reliably monitor the evolving needs of stakeholders regarding advancements in circular building construction technology, encompassing development, utilization, and associated applications.
2. Identify the key RECONSTRUCT stakeholders instrumental in determining the most appropriate formats and channels for disseminating information to specific target groups. The overarching objective is to enhance the potential for replication and utilization of tools honed within RECONSTRUCT, both during and, crucially, after the project's conclusion.
3. Articulate the core messages intended to apprise stakeholders of the objectives and eventual outcomes of RECONSTRUCT, fostering a deeper understanding among pertinent parties regarding the project's primary aims.
4. Develop an array of dissemination strategies, channels, initiatives, and resources aimed at achieving anticipated impacts in terms of awareness, engagement, and fostering acceptance, thereby bolstering the adoption of the project's results.
5. Define the internal processes within the consortium, encompassing activity schedules, task assignments, and responsibilities for all participating partners. This ensures the effective execution of dissemination, communication, and endeavours.

With that said, the project objectives will be met through strong and efficient strategy for dissemination, communication, and. The Communication component of the project will enable RECONSTRUCT to connect and engage with all targets, including end-users, by utilizing the communication tools developed during the project. Meanwhile, the Dissemination aspect will make it possible to reach out to professional stakeholders via selected channels and events.

The current document (D7.2) will serve as a guide to describe how the communication and dissemination activities will take place during the project, presenting processes, targets, tools, methods, and formats that will be used during its implementation.

The second version of this deliverable, namely D7.5 “Plan of the Dissemination and Communication activities - 2nd version”, will be released in M24. A final version will follow M48.

5 Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication

5.1 Preliminary Key Exploitable Results

Table 3. Preliminary Key Exploitable Results (KERs)

Key Exploitable Result	Owner(s)	Type of KER	Exploitation strategy
Digital system for sourcing secondary materials			
KER1 Image processing tools	BUL, ICCS	Software	SaaS subscription model
KER2 Portable HSI solution	UNIVPM, IRIS	Design	Internal use, licensing
KER3 User Interface System (UIS) decision-support tool	SYM, ICCS	Software	SaaS subscription model
Circular construction materials			
KER4 AAC, AACC, and TRRC	CTC, VUB, SOR	Formulation	Direct sales, licensing
Circular construction components			
KER5 Precast and Prefab elements	SOR, HOL	Design	Licensing, internal use
Digitization of material flows and digital twinning			
KER6 Digital Product Passport	ITEC	Software	Licensing
KER7 BIM-based Digital Twin	TEE	Model	Licensing
KER8 RECONSTRUCT SaaS	IRIS	Software	SaaS subscription model
Fully circular real-scale buildings			
KER9 Belgian Demo	HOL, VUB	Design	Freely available
KER10 Spanish Demo	COM, INC, CTC	Design	Freely available
Framework for circular construction			
KER11 Digital Stakeholder Platform	IRIS	Software	SaaS subscription model
KER12 Regional Roadmaps	ICO, INC, VUB	Publication	Freely available
KER13 RECONSTRUCT framework	SOO	Publication	Freely available
KER14	VUB	Publication	Freely available

Circular Business Models			
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5.2 Target audiences and key stakeholders

5.2.1 Preliminary Stakeholder Mapping

Stakeholders are individuals, organizations, or businesses with a vested interest in the project and its technologies. A comprehensive mapping of stakeholders is fundamental to develop an effective Dissemination strategy: identifying their needs and priorities allows to effectively plan Dissemination activities.

Table 4: RECONSTRUCT stakeholders' groups

	Stakeholder macro-groups	Stakeholders
1.	Polymakers and public authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European institutions and agencies • Standardisation bodies • National and local authorities
2.	Construction value chain actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raw material suppliers • Architecture Engineering and Construction (AEC) companies • Real estate developers • Materials and components manufacturers • Logistics providers • Contractors and builders • Retrofit and renovation companies • Demolition companies • Waste management and recycling companies
3.	Software technology developers and providers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning developers and providers • BIM and Digital Twin technology developers and providers • MAPO technology developers and providers • SaaS developers and providers
4.	Hardware technology manufacturers and providers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Construction equipment manufacturers • Modular building component manufacturers • IoT and sensors technology suppliers • Green building technology providers
5.	Data Management companies	
	Technology service providers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IT consulting firms • Cybersecurity service providers

7.	Financial actors and investors	Public and private investors
8.	Clusters, associations, and interest groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU-funded projects and initiatives • Industry associations
9.	Research & academia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research institutions and centres • Education institutions and universities • R&D departments of companies
10.	Civil society	Building users, homeowners and renters, European citizens, NGOs
11.	Media	Regional, national, and international media Specialised press

5.3 Key messages

The project's target groups are carefully identified based on their specific interests in the innovations resulting from the project. These groups encompass:

- 1) **Policy makers:** policymakers are a primary audience, as they will be keenly interested in the policy briefs stemming from the project's technological advancements.
- 2) **Construction Value Chain Actors:** this group plays a crucial role in the project's scope, given their direct involvement in the construction industry.
- 3) **Software Technology Developers and Providers:** focusing on the development and provision of software solutions, these stakeholders are pivotal due to their specialization in the project's technology domain.
- 4) **Technology Service Providers:** this group holds a significant interest in the project's outcomes, as they are crucial to the practical implementation of technological solutions.
- 5) **Financial Actors and Investors:** this category represents a critical audience to the project's success, as the innovation's adoption will necessitate investment from interested partners.
- 6) **Clusters and Associations:** these groups are also targeted, as their support and collaboration will be pivotal for the project's advancements and broader acceptance.
- 7) **Research and Academia:** Research institutions and academic organizations constitute another vital audience due to their interest in the scientific research promoted by the project.
- 8) **Media and Civil Society:** while somewhat secondary in the project's communication and dissemination strategy, these groups remain of interest, albeit to a lesser extent, due to their potential role in raising awareness and societal change and engagement.

In summary, the project's targeted audiences encompass a diverse range of stakeholders, each with a distinct role to play in the successful dissemination and adoption of its innovations.

5.3.1 Key messages at the general level

The following list and table provide an overview of RECONSTRUCT key messages:

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1. RECONSTRUCT will develop comprehensive, viable circular alternatives to ordinary steel and cement reducing its carbon footprint.
2. RECONSTRUCT will minimize material wastage in the construction industry, efficiently using existing resources.
3. RECONSTRUCT will develop reusable and recyclable materials with minimum virgin content.
4. RECONSTRUCT offers a comprehensive circular solution, from design to valorization routes.
5. RECONSTRUCT will design modular components designed for disassembly and reuse.
6. RECONSTRUCT will create a digital ecosystem for the sourcing of waste materials.

To address each target audience effectively, the project must craft key messages that convey its core goals by incorporating specific keywords and tailoring messages, ensuring that RECONSTRUCT resonates with them.

Key messages are short, direct, and easy-to-remember messages, specifically developed for each targeted stakeholder group. They drive the project's C&D effort by conveying the core concepts and ideas the project wants to communicate. The RECONSTRUCT key messages are gathered in the table below together with relevant taglines. In addition, the geographical area of each stakeholder is identified.

5.3.2 Key messages at the project and stakeholder level

Table 5: Key Messages at Stakeholder level

Target	Key Message	Tagline	Geographic Level
Construction Value Chain Actors	Concrete without OPC is not only possible but is a valid circular option.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CIRCULARITY • MATERIALS 	International
	Reconstruct aims to be the solution towards increased circularity in the building construction sector.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CIRCULARITY 	International European Regional
	Reconstruct will maximise the use of existing resources.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WASTE AS RESOURCE • MATERIALS 	National Regional
	RECONSTRUCT offers a complete circular solution, from design to valorization routes.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CIRCULARITY • CLUSTER • DESIGN 	International
	RECONSTRUCT will decrease carbon emissions within the construction sector.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • REDUCTION OF POLLUTION • MATERIALS • GREEN ECONOMY 	International

	RECONSTRUCT closes the loop by embedding deconstruction in building design.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DECONSTRUCTION • SUSTAINABILITY THROUGH TECHNOLOGY 	International
	RECONSTRUCT will trigger interoperability among waste management systems.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WASTE AS RESOURCE • SUSTAINABILITY THROUGH TECHNOLOGY 	Regional
Policymakers and Public Authorities	RECONSTRUCT will combine economic and social growth in the construction sector.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GREEN ECONOMY • SOCIAL GROWTH THROUGH INNOVATION 	European National Regional
	RECONSTRUCT can encourage new legislation or highlight possible areas of improvement of circular construction policies.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CIRCULARITY • RECONSTRUCTING OUR POLICIES 	European National Regional
Financial Actors and Investors	RECONSTRUCT's results are economically sustainable and profitable.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WASTE AS RESOURCE • SUSTAINABILITY THROUGH TECHNOLOGY 	European National Regional
	RECONSTRUCT will increase the lives of building components.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SUSTAINABILITY THROUGH TECHNOLOGY 	European National Regional
	RECONSTRUCT will maximize efficiency and reduce waste in the construction sector.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DESIGN • EFFICIENCY IN DIGITALISATION 	International
Software Technology Developers and Providers	RECONSTRUCT will produce extensive databases for monitoring buildings and waste sourcing.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SUSTAINABILITY THROUGH TECHNOLOGY • CIRCULARITY EMBEDDED IN DESIGN 	International
	RECONSTRUCT will develop new recyclable materials.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CIRCULARITY EMBEDDED IN DESIGN • MATERIALS • WASTE AS RESOURCE 	International
Designers	RECONSTRUCT will establish digital ecosystems to maximise existing resources.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WASTE AS RESOURCE • MATERIALS 	National Regional

Clusters, and associations	RECONSTRUCT will develop new recyclable materials.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CIRCULARITY EMBEDDED IN DESIGN • MATERIALS • WASTE AS RESOURCE 	International
	RECONSTRUCT will produce extensive databases to power its softwares for monitoring buildings, as well as source and appreciate waste.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SUSTAINABILITY THROUGH TECHNOLOGY • CIRCULARITY EMBEDDED IN DESIGN 	International
	Concrete without OPC is not only possible but is a valid circular option.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CIRCULARITY • MATERIALS 	International
Civil Society	RECONSTRUCT will reduce emissions and allow greater circularity in the construction sector.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GREEN ECONOMY • WASTE AS RESOURCE 	European National Regional
Media	RECONSTRUCT will decrease carbon emissions within the sector.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GREEN ECONOMY • WASTE AS RESOURCE 	European National Regional
Hardware Technology Manufacturers and Providers	Reconstruct will increase the demand for specialised deconstruction equipment.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CIRCULARITY • WASTE AS RESOURCE • DECONSTRUCTION 	International
Data Management companies	RECONSTRUCT improves the accuracy and efficiency of waste quantification and characterization.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CIRCULARITY EMBEDDED IN DESIGN • WASTE AS RESOURCE 	International
Technology Service Providers	RECONSTRUCT will optimize the construction and deconstruction processes.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CIRCULARITY EMBEDDED IN DESIGN • SECTORIAL SYNCRETISM 	International
	RECONSTRUCT improves the accuracy and efficiency of waste quantification and characterization.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CIRCULARITY EMBEDDED IN DESIGN • WASTE AS RESOURCE 	International
Waste management systems	RECONSTRUCT will boost interoperability among waste management systems.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WASTE AS RESOURCE • SECTORIAL SYNCRETISM 	Regional

Developers of similar technologies	RECONSTRUCT aims to promote cross-sectoral collaboration.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SECTORIAL SYNCRETISM 	Regional National International
	RECONSTRUCT aims to boost interoperability among waste management systems.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WASTE AS RESOURCE • SECTORIAL SYNCRETISM 	Regional National International

These key messages will be used and further elaborated into contents and the related appropriate formats for the project’s communication and dissemination channels and products, which will be presented in detail in the next sections.

5.4 A tailored approach to Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation

The project will implement a four stage-strategy: Engage, Produce, Share, and Exchange. Dissemination and Communication are crucial in the "Share," "Exchange," and "Engage" stages.

Figure 1: CDE Methodology

Dissemination shares the project’s results with scientists, policymakers, and businesses. Its main goal is to support science, bring people together, and help make informed policies for long-term benefits.

Communication makes the project and its findings more visible to the public. It uses easy-to-understand language to make people interested in the project’s topic and show how RECONSTRUCT can improve their lives in the long run.

Table 6: Difference between dissemination and communication

	Dissemination	Communication
Objectives	Public disclosure of scientific and technical results	Promotion of the project and its benefits
Audience	Professional target groups, such as scientific communities, industry stakeholders, policy makers, etc.	General public, including EU citizens, civil society
Tone of voice	Scientific/technical language	Non-specialized/layman's terms
Channels	Peer-review journals, scientific conferences, sector events, the web	The web, social networks, journalistic articles

In coordination with communication and dissemination efforts, exploitation activities will focus on setting the stage for the utilization of the developed technological solutions once the project concludes.

The table below explains how the project will communicate with different stakeholder groups. The project will customize the content and use the most effective methods and channels based on each stakeholder's needs.

Table 7: Exploitation, Dissemination and Communication actions

Stakeholders	Dissemination formats	Communication channels	How DC supports exploitation
Construction Value Chain Actors (including designers)	Scientific publications Info-packs Press Releases News Releases Webinars Video	Website Social Media Journalistic Articles Newsletter	RECONSTRUCT will change the way the construction sector works. They need to be informed of the new materials, capabilities for recycling, disassembly, and circularity in general. D&C will support post-project exploitation efforts for widespread adoption. The key is to build trust in secondary materials.
Policymakers and Public Authorities	Policy briefs Press Releases News Releases Webinars	Website Social Media Journalistic Articles Newsletter	These stakeholders can influence the regulatory environment for the development and application of the project's results. They will be recipients of the policy briefs, aimed at developing or improving regulations and providing recommendations for future policy decisions and directives.

Financial Actors and Investors	Press Releases News Releases Webinars Video	Website Social Media Journalistic Articles	Financial actors may be engaged because of their interest in investing in circular construction projects, and their funding might be pivotal in project development.
Software Technology Developers and Providers	Scientific Publications Info-packs	Website Social Media Journalistic Articles Newsletter	These stakeholders will be exposed to dissemination about the circular, digitalized construction sector, which represents business opportunities for them.
Research and Academia	Scientific publications Info-Packs Policy Briefs	Website Social Media Journalistic Articles Newsletter	Scientific papers produced by RECONSTRUCT will enable knowledge-transfer to the scientific community; and will continue the dialogue on circularity in the construction sector.
Clusters, and associations	Policy Briefs Press Releases News Releases Video	Website Social Media Journalistic Articles Newsletter	Through sharing best practices, lessons learned, and research findings from the project, RECONSTRUCT will reach out to other EU-funded projects to jointly develop evidence-based policies. Also, industry associations may want to promote new market opportunities among their members.
Civil Society	Press Releases News Releases Video	Website Social Media Journalistic Articles	Citizens will be engaged predominantly through local activities at the demonstrator sites. In turn, they will benefit from an increased attractiveness of job opportunities in the construction sector.
Media	Press Releases News Releases Video	Website Social Media Journalistic Articles	Exposure to local, national, and EU media will give more prominence to circularity in general, increase awareness and local engagement.
Hardware Technology Manufacturers and Providers	Scientific Publications Info-packs Webinars	Website Social Media Journalistic Articles Newsletter	Reaching these stakeholders about the circular, digitalized construction sector, is key for awareness and supporting adoption of circular practices.

Technology Service Providers including data management companies	Scientific Publications Info-packs Webinars	Website Social Media Journalistic Articles Newsletter	Exposing these stakeholders to dissemination activities ensures their involvement and support in the smooth operation of software and hardware technologies.
Developers of similar technologies	Scientific Publications Info-packs Webinars	Website Social Media Journalistic Articles Newsletter	The technologies developed in RECONSTRUCT can be of interest for other sectors, hence the importance to engage them in D&C activities.

5.5 Dissemination and communication channels

Table 8: Dissemination and Communication channels at the target level

Channel	Description	Target
Landing page	RECONSTRUCT's landing page was launched in July 2023 (M2) to offer an initial gathering point while the official website is under construction. It was created following the newly developed project's visual identity.	ALL
Website	RECONSTRUCT's website will be the main source of information for interested partners and stakeholders, and it will be launched in November 2023 (M6).	ALL
Social networks (Twitter, LinkedIn)	RECONSTRUCT will reach its community through social media channels, with updates about the project's results and engaging in dialogue with its followers.	ALL
Media multipliers	External platforms will republish journalistic articles, news and press releases written by RECONSTRUCT.	Researchers, industry stakeholders, citizens, policymakers

5.5.1 Website and landing page

RECONSTRUCT's website will serve as a primary communication and dissemination channel for the project, acting as the entry point for stakeholders, partners, and the general public.

This website will adapt and evolve to the project's needs, ensuring continued sharing of RECONSTRUCT's developments. Updates will be published on the "News and Events" pages, with content generated by ICONS and supported by project partners. The aim is to

provide clear, scientifically accurate information that is easily understandable by a broad audience.

The website will be developed using a user-experience design approach to enhance user navigation and help key stakeholders find the information most relevant to them.

Additionally, dissemination materials tailored for professionals will encompass all public deliverables produced by the project, along with updates on RECONSTRUCT activities. These materials are intended to capture the attention of relevant stakeholders, and to keep them informed about the project's results.

For the general public, RECONSTRUCT communication products will include press releases and graphic materials designed to raise awareness and interest in the project's outcomes.

In summary, the project website will serve the following purposes:

- Share RECONSTRUCT materials, including public deliverables and scientific publications.
- Provide access to communication materials, such as information packs and tutorials.
- Publish project news.
- Establish connections with external platforms, relevant initiatives, and related projects.
- Offer information about project events, webinars, workshops, and stakeholder engagement activities.
- Keep users informed about project activities and targeted dissemination initiatives.

The website will be developed using WordPress, ensuring easy content management during and after the project. The expected publication date for the project website is November 2023 (Month 6).

Table 9: Website accountability

Accountability	Developed and managed by ICONS, with input and feedback from all the partners. Input and cooperation from the rest of the RECONSTRUCT partnership will be encouraged during the project duration. To comply with General Data Protection Regulation – Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR), private data will remain confidential as ICONS will act as the Data Controller and be responsible for treating all the sensitive data provided by registered users upon online registration.
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5.5.2 Social networks

RECONSTRUCT will utilize social media platforms to promote its objectives and results, enhancing the reach of its communication and dissemination efforts.

The project will leverage social media channels as primary interfaces for engaging with the public, sharing content, and participating in campaigns.

LinkedIn and Twitter are chosen as the primary platforms for specific audiences. Policy makers, construction contractors, designers, researchers, and engaged citizens will be reached through these platforms.

Twitter is suitable for real-time updates on project progress, partner initiatives, milestones, and relevant articles.

LinkedIn will instead host official content, including news articles, press releases, milestones, event promotions, and partner activities.

The content strategy aligns with these platforms and audiences, ensuring that each social media channel effectively communicates the project's goals and achievements while engaging with its diverse stakeholders.

Table 10: Content delivery strategy summary, depending on the social media channel

	Twitter	LinkedIn
Target audiences	Construction Contractors Designers Software and Hardware developers Policy makers Researchers Citizens Media	Construction Contractors Designers Software and Hardware developers Researchers
Content type	Tweet and retweets	Posts and post shares
Main topics for content	Project milestones and organic news	Project milestones and organic news
	Partner milestones and news	Partner milestones and news
	External news and articles; Policy updates	Policy updates
	News and events of other related projects and initiatives (funded by the EU)	External news and articles (B&I developments in the field)

An official hashtag, #RECONSTRUCT_EU, has been established for the project to monitor the impact of the project's reach beyond ICONS's management. This hashtag will be utilized to track posts related to RECONSTRUCT and collect both quantitative and qualitative data regarding its social media impact.

Table 11: Social media accountability

Accountability	ICONS will be responsible for the core social media activities, like setting up the accounts, posting, following existing social media channels, and monitoring outreach.
	The consortium partners are encouraged to contribute by joining the community of the RECONSTRUCT Twitter and LinkedIn followers. They can retweet and repost our content from their organizations' channels and use the #RECONSTRUCT_EU hashtag.

KPI: at least 800 followers between Twitter and LinkedIn will be acquired.

5.5.2.1 Social media campaigns

RECONSTRUCT aims to initiate at least one social media campaign each year throughout the project implementation. These campaigns may be coordinated with other initiatives related to the CCRI and in collaboration with sister projects.

Social media campaigns serve the purpose of reinforcing and actively engaging the project's followers, fostering interaction with the content shared on social media platforms. These campaigns typically revolve around a specific theme or agenda and are designed to highlight particularly innovative content, setting it apart from regular posts.

5.5.3 E-newsletter

The project will produce a newsletter, which will be published online every six months and shared with those who register on the project's website. These newsletters are especially effective for engaging with professionals and the scientific community.

Businesses, research stakeholders, and policymakers can use the newsletter to stay updated on the project's progress. It also serves as a valuable tool to foster cooperation with similar projects, partnerships, and industry clusters through collaborative initiatives and connections.

The newsletter will be in English and will be also published on the website.

Table 12: Newsletter accountability

Accountability	<p>ICONS will collect content, write and create the newsletter and will take care of dispatching it to the online registered users. All project partners are encouraged to send in relevant news and events to be included in the newsletter.</p> <p>KPI: 1 newsletter every six months will be published.</p>
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5.5.4 Media multipliers

RECONSTRUCT will utilize external media partners to share project-related content of general interest.

These media partners have syndication agreements with ICONS, and the primary ones include EU Agenda, AlphaGalileo, and Phys.org. Additional channels focusing on RECONSTRUCT's themes will also be added to the distribution list, for example, BUILD UP. The content to be distributed includes journalistic articles, video interviews, and press releases about RECONSTRUCT.

The RECONSTRUCT consortium is encouraged to share project press releases through their own networks, and they should inform ICONS when they do so for monitoring purposes. All project communication materials will be regularly monitored to measure their reach and gauge the level of engagement they generate.

User contact details will be treated with strict confidentiality in accordance with GDPR regulations. ICONS will serve as the Data Controller for personal data collected through the project website, ensuring the protection of stakeholders' and users' sensitive information. Additionally, user contact details will be used solely for RECONSTRUCT dissemination, granting users access to their provided information and the option to opt-out from project communications at any time.

Table 13: Multipliers accountability

Accountability	ICONS will be responsible for distributing the news and press releases and journalistic articles to external news multipliers. The consortium partners are encouraged to re-distribute these materials within their networks.
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5.5.5 Youris.com

The youris.com portal is a significant multimedia platform that consolidates audiovisual and news content related to European science, innovation, policy, and research. This content is tailored for web, social media, and TV distribution. ICONS owns and manages this portal, keeping it regularly updated with news, journalistic articles, and video news releases (VNR) concerning European Research and Innovation.

The portal encompasses a wide range of research fields and has a track record of effectively amplifying content produced by numerous European-funded projects. RECONSTRUCT journalistic articles and interviews will be shared on both the project's website and youris.com. This dual publication significantly enhances the visibility of the content.

5.5.6 Partners corporate websites

RECONSTRUCT partners are encouraged to help spread project content through their own websites. ICONS has made connections with the communication officers of partner organizations and will send them the project's editorial materials for potential use.

The list of the project partners' social media channels in Table 4.11.

Table 14: Partner's corporate websites

Institution	Website	Facebook	Twitter	Youtube	Instagram	LinkedIn
INSTITUT DE TECNOLOGIA DE LA CONSTRUCCION DE CATALUNYA (ITeC)	https://itec.cat/	https://www.facebook.com/itec1978	https://twitter.com/ITeC_cat	https://www.youtube.com/itectv	https://www.instagram.com/itec_community/	https://www.linkedin.com/company/itec1978/

HOLLAND COMPOSITES (HOL) BV	https://www.hollandcomposites.nl/	https://www.facebook.com/hollandcomposites/	https://twitter.com/hollandcomposit			https://www.linkedin.com/company/unavailable/
ASOCIACION EMPRESARIAL DE INVESTIGACION TECNOLÓGICO DE LA CONSTRUCCION REGION DE MURCIA (CTC)	https://ctconrm.com/es	https://www.facebook.com/pages/Centro-Tecnol%C3%B3gico-de-la-Construcci%C3%B3n-Regi%C3%B3n-de-Murcia/253005478047045?sk=wall	https://twitter.com/CTCON	https://www.youtube.com/user/CTCONRM		https://www.linkedin.com/company/centro-tecnologico-de-la-construccion-region-de-murcia/
SIMBIOSY INDUSTRIAL SL (SYM)	https://www.simbiosy.com/		https://twitter.com/simbiosy			https://www.linkedin.com/company/simbiosy-sl/
UNIVERSITA POLITECNICA DELLE MARCHE (UNIVPM)	https://www.univpm.it/Entra/	https://www.facebook.com/UNIVPM	https://twitter.com/UnivPoliMarche	https://www.youtube.com/user/UNIVPM1	https://www.instagram.com/univpm/	https://www.linkedin.com/school/universita-politecnica-delle-marche/
COMSA SAU (COM)	https://www.comsa.com/		https://twitter.com/comsa_corp	https://www.youtube.com/c/COMSA_Corporacion		https://www.linkedin.com/company/comsa-corporacion/
IRIS TECHNOLOGY SOLUTIONS, SOCIEDAD LIMITADA (IRIS)	https://www.iris-eng.com/it/		https://twitter.com/iris_rd	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC54W3WtsD6JF		https://www.iris-eng.com/it/

				1Y8tVG1Flbg		
ACSA OBRAS E INFRAESTRUCTURAS SAU (SOR)	https://www.sorigue.com/es		https://twitter.com/sorigue		https://www.instagram.com/sorigue	https://www.linkedin.com/company/acsa-obras-e-infraestructuras-s.a./
VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL (VUB)	https://www.vub.be/nl	https://www.facebook.com/VUBrusseel	https://twitter.com/vubrusseel	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCxr4eNyQVz-7Qcf3K7lxp3g	https://www.instagram.com/vubrusseel/	
SOCIETAT ORGANICA +10 SCCL (SOO)	https://societatorganica.com/	https://www.facebook.com/societatorganica/	https://twitter.com/societatorganica		https://www.instagram.com/societatorganica/	https://www.linkedin.com/company/societat-organica/
EREVNITIKO PANEPISTIMIAKO INSTITOUTO SYSTIMATON EPIKOINONION KAI YPOLGISTON-EMP (ICCS)	https://www.iccs.gr/					free
INSTITUT CATALA DEL SOL (INC)	https://incasol.gencat.cat/ca/inici		https://twitter.com/incasolcat	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCP-5hgcl-2RcPR6WekzOMw	https://www.instagram.com/incasolcat/	https://www.linkedin.com/company/incasol/
GREEN ENERGY PARK (GEP)	https://www.ernet-smartenergysystems.eu/ll/700/Green-Energy-park---Smart-					

Multi-Energy-Lab.html						
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5.6 Dissemination and communications materials and formats

In RECONSTRUCT, ICONS will produce specific content formats and distribute them through dedicated channels to maximize awareness, acceptance, and adoption. These materials will include:

Table 15: Dissemination and communication materials and formats

Material/Format	Description	Target
Communication Kit	RECONSTRUCT's communication kit will include a leaflet, roll-up, a PowerPoint presentation and a presentation video, in line with the project's visual identity. These materials will be available online as download from the website, and offline as physical objects to be displayed at project's events, workshops and exhibitions.	All
Scientific publications	RECONSTRUCT's results will be supported by scientific publications. Articles and papers will be published in free and open access peer-reviewed journals and conference proceedings.	Research and Academia
Info-packs	Info-packs will be produced to present the project's results in a concise and technical manner.	Construction Stakeholders
Policy Briefs	These documents will gather recommendations and key policy inputs for the EU agenda on circular transition (e.g. EU Green Deal, Circular Economy Action Plan, etc.)	Policy Makers
Local desks	The demo cases in Brussels and Barcelona will set up dedicated local c&d desks aiming to establish continuous interaction with local stakeholders to promote the project's activities and results, Communication will mostly take place in local language. ICONS will give support and supervise this activity.	All

5.6.1 Communication kit

The RECONSTRUCT communication kit consists of high-quality materials designed to promote the project while maintaining its visual identity and key messages.

It includes a leaflet, a roll-up, a PowerPoint presentation, and one project presentation video. The purpose of this kit is to offer current information, facilitate result dissemination to the general public, and convey the project's objectives, challenges, and benefits in a clear and accessible manner to a broad audience.

These resources from the communication kit will support project communication by serving as engaging tools for RECONSTRUCT partners, especially during events. They contain comprehensive project information necessary for stakeholders. All visual materials will be available in digital format for easy downloading.

Table 16: Communication kit accountability

Accountability	<p>ICONS will oversee the development and the design of materials. WP leaders will revise texts and provide feedback. All partners will provide further information that may be necessary for the development of the kit.</p> <p>All partners are responsible for translations of their materials, if needed; ICONS will provide the translations template and take care of layout adjustments.</p> <p>All partners have budget for communication activities which can include printing costs. ICONS will provide the documents for printing.</p> <p>KPI: at least 500 leaflets downloaded, at least 500 leaflets distributed</p>
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5.6.1.1 Roll-up

The roll-up poster is a visually appealing display designed to grab the attention of stakeholders. It features the project logo, a catchy slogan, details about the project website and social media links, an email contact, and information about the consortium members. This poster will be produced in the standard roll-up size of 200x80cm and will be showcased at RECONSTRUCT workshops, focus groups, and physical events where project representatives are present-

5.6.1.2 Leaflet

The leaflet is meant to inform individuals about the project, its objectives, and its primary activities. It was chosen over a flyer due to its ability to effectively convey technical information. Consortium members will distribute the leaflet at events, and it will be available in English.

In line with the project's visual identity, the leaflet adheres to the same standards. It offers comprehensive yet brief details about crucial project aspects: its primary objective, key components, advantages for the stakeholder community, and partner information with contact details.

Both print and digital formats are available for the leaflet, with a preference for the digital version whenever feasible. As a result, it is crucial for the leaflet to be visually engaging and effective when viewed online.

5.6.1.3 Presentation video

The RECONSTRUCT presentation video serves as a connection between the project and its audience. It offers a sneak peek into the project's early stages, even before most technical activities are in full swing. Its primary goal is to boost awareness and engage the viewers. This video is tailored for a wide audience, so it adopts an informal tone and uses clear and straightforward language to effectively communicate its message.

5.6.2 Scientific and technical publications

The project aims to produce valuable scientific results suitable for presentation at conferences and publication in journals. RECONSTRUCT papers will highlight the most significant findings from the project. Open-access publication is accounted for by the project. News about the release of RECONSTRUCT's scientific and peer-reviewed publications will be posted on the project website and social media channels.

Table 17: Scientific publications accountability

Accountability	<p>Research and technical partners will be the main responsible for the release and publishing of these actions.</p> <p>ITeC will keep track of all the scientific and technical publications made by RECONSTRUCT's scientific and technical partners within the project. Moreover, ICONS will promote such publications via the project website and social media.</p> <p>KPI: at least 8 articles will be published on top rank peer-reviewed journals</p>
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5.6.3 Info-packs and innovation handbook

Info-packs, in the form of fact- and info-sheets or concise reports, are tailored for professionals to grasp the project's technical insights, solutions, and outcomes.

These documents allow the ICONS communication team to present technical accomplishments and findings in an appealing, easily accessible format. They will extract content from public deliverables and scientific publications generated by the project.

Info-packs are well-suited for distribution at scientific and technical events. Additionally, they will be accessible for download from the project website and actively shared with key stakeholder groups interested in staying updated on project results.

All RECONSTRUCT's info-packs will be collected in the final Innovation Handbook, that will deliver in its final form all the project's scientific innovations.

Table 18: info packs and innovation handbook accountability

Accountability	<p>ICONS will oversee the development and the graphic design of the info-packs. When the content of the factsheets will be particularly technical, some partners or the coordinator will be asked to draft content, based on the guidelines provided by ICONS, who will oversee the final edits and pagination. At least one info-pack per addressed target audience will be developed.</p> <p>KPI: at least 1 info-pack per target group will be released.</p>
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5.6.4 Policy briefs

A policy brief is a concise document that offers essential information and actionable policy recommendations on a specific issue. RECONSTRUCT will use policy briefs to give policy-makers solid scientific ground on which discussions and plans can be made for the EU agenda on circular transition, as well as the EU Green Deal and the Circular Economy Action Plan.

Table 19: Policy briefs accountability

Accountability	<p>ITeC will oversee the content of policy briefs. Once approved, ICONS will design tailored formats for dissemination.</p> <p>KPI: at least 1 policy brief and 2 presentations held at relevant EU premises will be released.</p>
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5.6.5 Webinars

Webinars are an effective tool for sharing project information, engaging a wider audience, and maximizing RECONSTRUCT's impact. They allow RECONSTRUCT to present its goals, progress, and outcomes in detail, while also encouraging active participation through live chat, Q&A sessions, polls, and interactive features. Training activities can also be carried out in the form of webinars.

Table 20: Webinar production accountability

Accountability	<p>Responsible partners will oversee the organization of webinars. ICONS will oversee the eventual dissemination of each webinar organised and</p>
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produced by the other partners, promoting this product both on the project's website and social media accounts.

KPI: at least 4 workshops/webinars will be organized in conjunction with big sectorial events

5.6.6 Local d&c desks

Local desks oversee communication and dissemination activities at local level. Two partners have been identified as leaders of the local desks: Green Energy Park for Brussels and INCASOL for Barcelona. They will organize local activities, ranging from general events, specific events, and workshops, engage local citizens and local sectoral stakeholders and collaborate with local media to ensure that relevant information on the local demo buildings reaches the correct audience. Their activities will be carried out in the local language mainly. To support their activities, the demo case studies sections of the website were translated into Spanish, while it was decided that this was not needed for the Brussels case study. Local desks will define part of the D&C strategy including the identification of the target audiences, and the appropriate channels and formats to be used to reach out towards them. ICONS will support them in the identification of the target audiences and the most suitable communication and dissemination channels and formats.

Additionally, each local desk should:

- Map and collect local content (i.e., events, initiatives, press releases, events, videos, flyers, etc.);
- Promote and circulate contents of the targets area.
- Organize and manage local engagement initiatives (citizens and stakeholders).
- Maximise outreach towards other areas within their country.
- Track and monitor D&C activities at the local level and share the info with WP7 leader (ICONS).

Table 21: Local C&D desks accountability

Accountability	<p>ICONS will oversee the management of the local desks and provide support if needed. ICONS will also monitor the local activities of each demonstrator. To this end, specific monitoring templates will be shared with the local desks' representatives.</p> <p>Each demonstrator lead will be responsible for organising local events and disseminating results locally in the local language.</p>
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5.7 Editorial contents

Table 22: Editorial Contents

Editorial content	Description	Target
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Journalistic articles	Professional journalists will produce independent articles and interviews to project's experts and external stakeholders, distributed afterwards to online media, thematic portals, and other information outlets.	Citizens, Construction Contractors, media
Press and news releases	Press and news releases inform the community about project achievements and events.	All
Video production	RECONSTRUCT videos will be distributed online for an easy and engaging communication towards all project audiences. These may be also used to present the project at sector events.	All
Webinars	The RECONSTRUCT live or pre-recorded webinars will deliver educational, informative, or promotional content on circular construction topics.	Designers, Construction value Chain actors, EU initiatives, academia

Each product's outreach will be monitored on a regular basis to get information about communication needs and to better target the project's audiences for future releases.

5.7.1 Journalistic articles and interviews

Professional journalists will create independent articles and conduct interviews related to RECONSTRUCT, framing them to appeal to a broad audience.

These articles will be published on the project website and further disseminated across European and global audiences through various media platforms, including EU Agenda, AlphaGalileo, and Phys.org, and BUILD UP. Social media channels will also promote these articles upon release.

These journalistic articles aim to inform and engage the public on topics related to the project. They serve as a bridge to present a technical project like RECONSTRUCT to a general audience using accessible language and messages. By raising public awareness and highlighting the project's key ideas, these articles and interviews will develop public interest in the project's topics.

Table 23: Journalistic articles accountability

Accountability	Contents will originate either from external sources collected by journalists (during their investigation) or directly from the RECONSTRUCT project. ICONS will take care of the distribution. KPI: 2 journalistic articles will be published.
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5.7.2 Press and project updates

RECONSTRUCT's press and news releases serve to capture the attention of stakeholders and the public, highlighting project progress and achievements.

Press releases are ideal for sharing major accomplishments, such as the release of scientific papers or technical deliverables.

News releases adopt instead a more informal structure and plain language, making them accessible to the general public. These releases are typically posted on the project website to share noteworthy updates, project features, and significant work. News releases are particularly effective when announcing the participation of RECONSTRUCT partners in external events to showcase their latest project findings or achievements.

In the case of news releases, RECONSTRUCT adopts a collaborative approach, with all partners contributing to editorial content related to WP7 activities. The diverse partnership offers a wide range of perspectives, both academic and practical.

Both press and news releases will be published on the project website and, when considered newsworthy, distributed to external online resources and news platforms.

Consortium members are encouraged to actively publish and share project-related news on their own distribution channels and external media. ICONS will monitor partner publications every six months.

Table 24: Press and news releases accountability

Accountability	<p>ICONS will be responsible for producing and distributing press releases on behalf of RECONSTRUCT.</p> <p>All the members of the RECONSTRUCT consortium will contribute by writing news releases. ICONS will organize and manage such production and take care of the distribution.</p> <p>Once press and news releases are ready, all the members of the consortium will be encouraged to further distribute them through their own portals, newsletters, or other appropriate channels.</p> <p>KPI: at least 8 press releases will be published.</p>
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5.7.3 Video production

RECONSTRUCT's video production aims to effectively communicate project objectives and activities. The videos will use animation, infographics, and real footage.

The RECONSTRUCT presentation video will be ready by January 2024 to simplify and promote the project topics for a wide audience. At least two video interviews for each demo-site will be produced, including footage from the demonstrators.

Videos are an effective way to share complex information and reach a wider audience. They will be promoted on social media, the project website, and relevant platforms. The RECONSTRUCT presentation video may also be used at external events.

Table 25: Video production accountability

Accountability	<p>ICONS will oversee the video production, development, and distribution. Format and content to be featured on the video will be preliminarily discussed with ITeC and the WP leaders. All partners will provide further materials that may be necessary for the development of the video.</p> <p>KPI: the videos will receive at least total 400 views.</p>
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5.8 Clustering, synergies and events

RECONSTRUCT partners will participate in networking events to increase project visibility among stakeholders. In-person events enhance interaction opportunities.

RECONSTRUCT will work in partnership with its sister projects CIRCBOOST and WOODCIRCLES, by organising joint dissemination activities, such as joint events and social media campaigns. To kick off and facilitate this collaboration, the cluster has applied for the Horizon Results Booster services Module A and Module B, aiming at supporting the Cluster's joint dissemination activities. First, a portfolio of research and innovation results will be created (D1.1, mod A) aiming to better identify the commonalities of the cluster members in terms of results and stakeholders. Then, a joint dissemination strategy will be developed and implemented, with the support of the HRB Experts team. In addition, Cluster joint dissemination materials (such as a video and factsheet) will be created by the HRB.

Moreover, RECONSTRUCT will actively collaborate with and participate in events, workshops and activities organised by the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI). In addition, the project will consider participation in other relevant EU initiatives in the construction sector (including the New European Bauhaus initiative).

Table 26: sister projects, networks and initiatives

Type	
CL6 – CIRCBO projects	CIRCBOOST WOODCIRCLES
Other projects	ReCreate, ICEBERG, HOUSEFUL, MOBICCON-PRO, CircThread, CodeDEMO, CISUFLO, NewWave, RECONMATIC, BIO4EEB, EASY ZERO, DESIRE, BEST, RECOMPOSE
Initiatives	CCRI (Circular Cities and Regions Initiative)

	European Bauhaus Initiative
Other	Horizon Results Booster

RECONSTRUCT events

Partners will track upcoming networking, clustering events, and scientific conferences and express their interest in representing RECONSTRUCT. Event participation will be monitored through ongoing communication within the consortium, with ICONS collecting updates every six months via a dedicated template. These events may include conferences, fairs, workshops, roundtables, and more on project-related topics. Project communication materials will be distributed at these events to support partners in promoting RECONSTRUCT. Partner attendance will be highlighted on the project website and social media channels for visibility.

Table 27: RECONSTRUCT technical & dissemination events

Event	Description	Target
vWorkshops	RECONSTRUCT will organize workshops to showcase key project results and outcomes from the demo-sites, host experts from the consortium, and broader stakeholders group. Training activities can also be organized.	Policy makers, Construction Value Chain Actors
Final event	The final event will showcase key project results and outcomes from the demo-sites, hosting experts from the consortium and broader stakeholder groups.	All
Other joint events with sister projects	RECONSTRUCT will organize joint dissemination events with sister projects funded under the same call.	Policy makers, local authorities, municipalities, researchers, business sector

Table 28: Events accountability

Accountability	<p>ITeC will oversee the clustering and networking events, contact initiatives, projects, and networks to multiply dissemination opportunities, organize joint events.</p> <p>ITeC will oversee the final event organization with the support of ICONS and the other project partners.</p> <p>ICONS will be responsible for keeping track of all the events in which representatives of the RECONSTRUCT partnership will participate.</p> <p>KPI: at least 8 conferences will be attended, and at least 3 poster presentations will be held.</p>
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5.9 Training

Communication and dissemination efforts will have the training program of relevant actors in the construction chain as an objective to ensure the knowledge and the achievements of the project will be transmitted in a correct, useful, and practical manner. A correct emphasis on training will also guarantee that the project's innovation will continue to be relevant and live afterwards RECONSTRUCT's conclusion.

Many activities and methods discussed above in this document are prone to being receptive vehicles for knowledge transfer: info-packs, webinars, sector conferences and workshops might be recorded and will thusly be written and organized with the idea of being moments for training the readers or the attendees, depending on the format.

This need will be especially important during the replication of results phase 4 (from Month 9 to month 48 of the project) as the project's results will be mature enough to provide useful materials to train construction actors onto.

5.9.1 Training modules

All the materials developed by other work packages (e.g. WP6) will be made available to professionals in the construction field in video form through the stakeholders' platform. These clips, may them be in the form of webinars, tutorials, video-interviews, opinions of experts, exc. will gathered to create a training programme.

This training programme will help professionals navigate through the topics that are consistently encountered in the field, and will have a modular nature: it will have both core and elective courses, as to choose the areas in which to specialize, and will be adaptable to any type of background the worker may possess in the field, as the scope of these courses is to target the entire construction value chain.

The training programme will be considered completed after seven weeks of 2-3 hour-sessions per week.

The training material (presentations, reports or videos recorded) will be available on the project website and/or on the digital stakeholder platform.

Table 29: Training Accountability

Accountability	<p>ITeC will oversee the training materials and the contents related to them. IRIS will develop the stakeholder platform that will host the training modules.</p> <p>Icons will be responsible for providing the templates and the guidelines for presenting such materials, but the content will be provided by the relevant partners.</p>
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KPI: 10 training modules will be released, and will be completed by at least 100 workers in the industry, depending on their expertise and role.

5.10 Management of communication and dissemination

5.10.1 Responsibility in the consortium

Effective EU communication requires strong cooperation between D&C Leader (ICONS) and the consortium to engage stakeholders and the public. The document emphasizes interconnections between project D&C activities and partners' local efforts, stressing full team cooperation.

WP7's successful execution relies on input from all RECONSTRUCT partners, including interviews and workshops facilitated by ICONS. Local D&C activities will be established in each community of the two demo sites, to better disseminate the specific regional interests of RECONSTRUCT. ITeC, ICONS, IRIS, INC, GEP and other RECONSTRUCT members have specific roles and responsibilities detailed in the document.

Table 30: RECONSTRUCT's partnership accountability in communication and dissemination

Partner	Responsibility and involvement
ITeC (Coordinator)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Validating the proposed PD&C. Enforcing the PD&C in support of ICONS. Providing input and feedback on some D&C products to be released on behalf of RECONSTRUCT (i.e., project video, leaflet). Making sure the content of PD&C formats is scientifically accurate, and in line with the research performed in the other WPs. Attending the WP7 meetings.
ICONS (WP7 leader)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Developing, leading and monitoring the D&C activities; Defining key messages that will convey the objectives and goals of RECONSTRUCT based on the needs and interests of the project's target audience; Developing the RECONSTRUCT visual identity and various communication materials i.e., leaflets, project video; Designing, updating and maintaining of the project website; Producing the content to be published on the project website and external channels, newsletters and social media platforms, together with the active contribution of all the partners; Monitoring the impact of communication materials produced and distributed for RECONSTRUCT; Delivering regular updates of the communication plan based on the project's emerging dissemination and communication requirements. Chairing WP7 WG meetings.
GEP, INC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Attending the Local D&C desk meetings; Establishing effective regional communication to further disseminate RECONSTRUCT's results;

	Work closely with the D&C leader (ICONS) as to effectively coordinate the communication efforts
All	Providing inputs to create the RECONSTRUCT website and other communication materials; Keeping ICONS informed as to relevant progress made by the project in their respective work packages; Boosting RECONSTRUCT's presence on social media; Providing timely ICONS with the list of events and publications they will be attending on behalf of RECONSTRUCT; Mobilizing networks and connections for a wider outreach and promotion of RECONSTRUCT;

5.10.2 Production: management, timing and feedback

ICONS is primarily responsible for producing Dissemination and Communication (DC) formats, managing communication channels, and ensuring content quality on RECONSTRUCT platforms, including final approval. Partners can offer input and feedback as prompted by ICONS, but ICONS has the final say on incorporating it. Once a product is final, no further edits can be made to meet deadlines while respecting ICONS' expertise.

ICONS has a dedicated team of professionals, including social media managers, web developers, graphic designers, video makers, analysts, and communication managers who work closely together.

Partners should provide feedback on graphic and aesthetic elements only if they misrepresent the project. The format of DC products aligns with content, ensuring the core message is not distorted, avoiding continuous edits.

Partners are encouraged to use the brand book independently, utilizing in-house designers or open-source programs like Canva.

The table below outlines ICONS' steps during production to enhance transparency and clarify partner responsibilities.

Table 31: DC production steps

Step	Editorial	Formats	Other dissemination efforts
1	The ICONS project manager (PM) initiates the task internally with graphic designers, video makers, and SMMs	The responsible partner (RP) initiates the task by contacting the ICONS PM or the ICONS PM initiates the task internally	The RP initiates the task by contacting the ICONS PM.
2	The PM collects input from partners	The RP collects input from partners	/
3	He/she contacts the accountable partner/s by sending the content to be revised	He/she contacts the accountable partner/s by sending the content to be revised	/
5	The PM collects feedback and finalises the text/script	The RP collects feedback and finalises the text/script	/

6	Editorial contents are proofread	Content for formats is proofread by the RP. ICONS might give language advice to align it to the project's tone of voice	/
7	The PM implements the language advice	The RP implements the language advice	/
8	Graphic design, SM distribution, video editing. Website, roll-up, leaflet: final texts are forwarded to the designer for the graphic production Press and news releases and journalistic articles and sent to the social media manger (SMM) for distribution on SM and towards media multipliers Video scripts are sent to video makers and designers for the shooting and post-production	Final content is sent to ICONS for editorial "packaging". ICONS forwards the final texts to graphic designers. The PM discusses with the team the best dissemination route for the format.	If relevant, ICONS writes a news/events release for the website. Noteworthy project news are distributed toward media multipliers by the SMM.
9	The final product is shared with the consortium and promoted through appropriate channels	The final product is shared with the consortium and promoted through appropriate channels	The final product is promoted through appropriate channels

To handle RECONSTRUCT production effectively, ICONS has established guidelines for partner requests, contributions, and timely delivery of DC formats. The following tables outline guidelines for specific formats, indicating who should be contacted for requests, who is responsible for delivery, the required delivery time, and who should be contacted for feedback.

The first table covers formats for which ICONS is directly responsible. While precise deadlines are mentioned in the DoA, this table provides estimates of production times for ICONS, considering the initiation of the task and any feedback loops. ICONS will always prioritize DoA deadlines when provided. The timing is specified in calendar months, weeks, or days.

5.10.3 ICONS Responsibilities

The following table gathers the responsibility, timing and feedback for each planned editorial content and the communication kit that will be produced.

Table 32: Responsibility, timing and feedback for the editorial content and communication kit

What	Responsible	Timing	Input	Feedback (content)
Video	ICONS / PM	2 months	All	TCD + WP leaders
Leaflet	ICONS / PM	2 months	TCD + WP leaders	TCD + WP leaders
Roll-up	ICONS / PM	1 months	TCD + WP leaders	TCD + WP leaders
Social media campaigns (organisation)	ICONS / PM & SMM	1.5 month	All, depending on the campaign	TCD and/or ICLEI
Short videos	ICONS / PM	2 months	All, depending on the video	TCD + WP leaders, all
Press releases	ICONS / PM	1-2 weeks	/	TCD
News & event releases, project updates	ICONS / PM	1-2 weeks	All, depending on the editorial content	/
Journalistic article	ICONS / PM & Editorial Manager	1-2 months, depending on the availability of the editorial manager	TCD; other involved partners	Contributing partners can review their quotes and give feedback on technical parts, upon request

The next table lists formats within ICONS' responsibility, particularly in graphic design and packaging. Content is provided by partners, already approved and proofread. The estimated timing considers graphic production and allows for one feedback iteration. The timeline is per item, so it may vary when producing multiple items simultaneously. Some formats use pre-existing templates. Post-production dissemination is not included and will be assessed by the PM and SMM.

Table 33: Responsibility, timing and feedback for the formats' production

What	Responsible	Timing (ICONS production)	Input	Feedback
Factsheets	ITeC, WP leaders	1 month (first release: 1.5)	ITeC, WP leaders	ITeC, WP leaders
Local media articles	All	1-2 weeks	All, depending on the article	ICONS
Policy briefs	All	2.5 month	All	ITeC, WP leaders

The final table presents formats where the initiative is expected to come from partners. The timing spans from when the request is received by the PM until publication on the website and dissemination through social media platforms. Certain requests may involve extra tasks, like drafting news releases. Please note that timing depends on ICONS personnel availability. Immediate delivery may not always be possible.

Table 34: Responsibility, timing and feedback for partner's dissemination efforts

What	Responsible	Contact	Timing
Open access publications	All	PM, SMM in cc	1-2 weeks
Conference presentations	All	PM, SMM in cc	1-2 weeks
Participation in key events	All	PM, SMM in cc	1-2 weeks
Request to share news/events on SM	All	PM, SMM in cc	1-2 weeks
Request to create a card for SM	All	PM, SMM in cc	1-2 weeks
Request to produce communication materials in local languages	All	PM	1-2 weeks

Regarding social media, ICONS is responsible for sourcing suitable stock photos, but partners are encouraged to share their own original and rights-free pictures from conferences and events. Two key considerations for event promotion:

- Time: Share updates and news during or shortly after an event with engaging content.
- Human Element: Feature yourself and colleagues in photos to establish a personal connection and engage the audience.

Printing assistance:

ICONS can help partners with limited printing funds for materials like leaflets, roll-ups, and factsheets. The PM will gather multiple quotes and printing takes 3-5 days, with shipping varying by destination (5-10 days). It's advisable to request materials at least one month in advance to ensure they arrive in time for events.

5.10.4 Stakeholder Database

The stakeholder mapping becomes crucial from the second year of the project, once significant results are ready for dissemination. This database can be updated at any time during the project upon specific notification to avoid data loss.

It will include GDPR-compliant information, stakeholder type (based on mapping priorities), the geographical reach of each stakeholder, relevant key exploitation results (KERs) for each stakeholder type, preferred dissemination channels and formats, and the partner responsible for dissemination.

Partners are expected to identify organizations in contact with RECONSTRUCT's key results in the populated database. The same partner identifying these organizations should

engage directly with them and manage the dissemination of project results. As the project progresses, partner organizations are encouraged to approach and engage with specific stakeholders, conveying more targeted messages and sharing project dissemination materials.

Moreover, partners, particularly task leaders, are responsible for identifying specific features or results that should be communicated to relevant stakeholders.

ICONS, in its role as C&D leader, provides support for overall project communication and assists individual partners in their outreach efforts.

5.11 Monitoring

The monitoring and impact assessment of RECONSTRUCT's communication and dissemination campaigns are crucial. They quantify impacts in terms of awareness and acceptance among the target stakeholder groups. High acceptance is vital for market adoption of the project's solutions.

ICONS employs a robust monitoring and impact assessment methodology, focusing on content distribution and engagement across all channels. It relies on a set of indicators designed to be:

- Measurable: Represented numerically for trend analysis.
- Easy to understand and use by partners.
- Repeatable and consistent throughout the project.
- Available from reliable online sources.
- Timely, reflecting each communication and engagement effort.
- Reliable, drawn from trusted online analytics sources.
- Insightful, offering insights into communication and engagement effectiveness.

Monitoring these indicators and assessing impacts are ongoing, allowing ICONS to make corrections and improvements as needed. The methodology is described briefly here, with more details provided in subsequent documents.

5.11.1 ICONS' monitoring process

ICONS' methodology is based on outreach and engagement indicators, calculated using data from web analytics and software tools. Outreach indicators gauge the reach of online and offline communications, contributing to awareness. Engagement indicators measure stakeholder interactions with content, indicating project acceptance.

These indicators cover all public content (news releases, articles, videos) and channels (websites, social media, news multipliers).

ICONS utilizes Matomo, a real-time monitoring platform, to track online content diffusion: "Total mentions" in Table 3.26 represent the frequency of content discovery across the web and social media that Matomo monitors (Twitter, WordPress, Google+, Blogs, News, RSS, Tumblr, Automattic, Reddit, VK, Facebook, Youtube).

The sums of indicators in Table 3.26 and Table 3.27 provide the total outreach and engagement values at the time of data collection. Ad-hoc indicators have been developed

to estimate outreach and engagement values for events, such as conferences and webinars, based on audience size.

Table 35: Outreach indicators for the assessment of the C&D campaigns

Channels	Outreach indicators	Tool
Website	Total visits on reconstruct-project.eu	MATOMO
	Unique visitors on reconstruct-project.eu	
	Total visits on youris.com	
	Unique visitors on youris.com	
Social media	Twitter impressions on @ReconstructEU	Twitter Analytics
	Twitter impressions on @YourIS_com	
	LinkedIn visualisations on @ReconstructEU	LinkedIn Statistics
	LinkedIn visualisations on @youris-com	
	Facebook visualisations on @youriscom	Facebook Statistics
	Visualisations on PROJECT YouTube channel	YouTube counter
News multipliers	Impressions on multipliers	Provided directly by the multipliers or, in a minor number of cases, estimates based on a solid number of parameters leveraging time series and historical data

Table 36: Engagement indicators for the assessment of the C&D campaigns

Channels	Engagement indicators	Tool
Website	Facebook likes and social shares on youris.com	youris.com social widget
Social media	Twitter engagements (clicks, likes, retweets, replies etc)	Twitter Analytics
	LinkedIn clicks, likes, comments and shares	LinkedIn Statistics
	YouTube likes and comments	YouTube counter
	Total mentions	NUVI

News multipliers	Multipliers' engagement metrics	Provided by the multipliers
Other	Other uptakes	Communicated by project partners to ICONS

5.11.2 ICONS' engagement indexes

Engagement reflects the level at which stakeholders actively interact with a project and its results. It's vital to evaluate how effective communication and stakeholder involvement are.

ICONS has crafted a methodology to observe stakeholder engagement. This involves constant monitoring of: (i) how a project's content is disseminated, and (ii) how stakeholders engage with the project through various communication methods on all channels. This approach measures the views and interactions associated with the project's content.

Outreach indicators: These gauge the reach of the content and aim to amplify awareness among targeted stakeholders. While important, these indicators, in isolation, don't give a full representation of how well a project communicates. They are more of a preliminary step for deeper analysis.

Engagement indicators: These metrics offer insights into the effectiveness of a project's content in sparking interest and achieving buy-in from target stakeholders. They measure stakeholder interactions, for instance, online engagements. These metrics are essential for determining the success of communication efforts.

Using both outreach and engagement metrics, ICONS introduced a comprehensive index known as the Community Engagement Index (CEI). This index combines five distinct metrics: the Website Engagement Index (WEI), Social Media Engagement Index (SEI), Publication Engagement Index (PEI), Webinar Engagement Index (WEEI), and Events Engagement Index (EEI).

The five aforementioned areas embody standard communication tasks undertaken by research initiatives. While these metrics can be aggregated, they can also be determined for specific or groups of channels, such as individual websites, social media platforms, publications, and events.

Each index's value is found by comparing its outreach and engagement metrics. For instance, the WEI is derived using the formula $WEI = ew/ow$, where "ew" represents the website engagement metric and "ow" symbolizes the website outreach metric.

Table 37: Monitoring accountability

Accountability	ICONS will oversee monitoring the outreach and engagement generated by the project communication. The outcome of such exercise will be shared with the RECONSTRUCT consortium at project meeting and it will feed into periodic reporting.
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5.11.3 Timeline

The table provided outlines WP7 activities from the project's initiation to Month 18, coinciding with the scheduled update of the Communication and Dissemination plan. During the initial months, the focus will be on establishing the project's visual identity, launching social media profiles, the project website, and outreach materials. Concurrently, Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and primary stakeholders will be identified based on the project proposal and input from all partner organizations.

Additionally, a sustained social media presence will be maintained, the RECONSTRUCT consortium community will be developed, and social media campaigns will run alongside the issuance of press releases, tied to significant project milestones, events, achievements, or deliverables.

For the subsequent period, spanning from Month 25 to Month 48, a detailed timeline will be provided in the updated document, to be released in December 2024, at Month 18.

Table 38: Dissemination and communication tracking table

When	What	Who
M1	Kick-off Meeting	All
M2	Visual Identity, Brand book, set up of social media, Landing Page	ICONS
M4	First Press Release, initial stakeholder Analysis, start of the partners presentation campaign	ICONS
M6	First version of the Communication and Dissemination Plan, First version of the website	ICONS
M8	Communication Kit, including video, leaflet, poster and power point. First newsletter release	ICONS
M12	Second Newsletter release	ICONS
M16	First joint policy brief	All
M18	End of first reporting period. Third Newsletter Release	ICONS

5.12 Visual identity

5.12.1 Project's visual identity

A compelling and cohesive visual project identity is crucial for effectively engaging with stakeholders and amplifying the project's influence and impact. The project logo is a product of the brand personality exercise for RECONSTRUCT, which focuses on the key attributes, qualities, and elements that project partners wish to communicate when representing the project.

Figure 2: Brand personality exercise results

The official brand book was developed and shared among partners. It serves as a rulebook for everyone involved in the project, particularly when developing communication and dissemination materials for specific events including webinars.

The brand book includes clear guideline to allow partners to use it autonomously. There are specifications regarding colour usage that explain which colours can be used together harmoniously, as well as examples of colour combinations to avoid. The brand book is also clear on photography usage, fonts to be utilise for official project’s products, and correct implementation of the logo.

Figure 3: Official RECONSTRUCT LOGO

Figure 4: Official RECONSTRUCT colour palette

6 Conclusions

The Plan of the Dissemination and Communication activities outlines RECONSTRUCT communication and dissemination strategy. Partners can use this document to align their own communication with the project's overarching plan. It also highlights the primary tools and channels that will be utilized throughout the project, along with the monitoring strategy that will be implemented.

The channels and formats detailed in this plan will help raise awareness and encourage engagement among professional stakeholders and the general public. We will periodically monitor their effectiveness and outreach, enabling us to refine and improve our content and overall strategy over time.

It should be noted that the current deliverable will be subject to future revisions in the Plan of the Dissemination and Communication activities - 2nd version (M24) in order to refine the strategy as the project progresses. The final version will be then delivered by the end of the project (M48).

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7 Annex 1 – Communication and dissemination activities templates

Table 39: Communication activities monitoring table

COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES						
Partner	Communication activity name	Description	Who?	How?	Outcome	Status
Choose your organisation from the list.	Insert communication name	Insert a short description of implemented communication activity. Max 200 characters spaces included.	Target audience. Please, choose between those included in the CDE plan (DX.X). You can refer to the 'Legend'. If more target audiences were addressed, please add as many lines as necessary.	Communication channel. Please refer to the 'Legend'.	Insert key performance indicators, if available in the DoA. If not available include NA	Choose from the list.

Table 40: Dissemination activities monitoring table

DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES						
1. Partner	2. Dissemination activity name	3. What?	4. Who?	5. Why?	6. Status	7. Estimated number of participants

Plan of the Dissemination and Communication activities - 1st version/D7.2

Choose your organisation from the list.	Type the title of the activity/event.	Choose the type of dissemination activity from the list. Please note that: - External meetings do not include the project meetings. - Clustering activities are those with cluster networks. - Collaborations with EU funded projects are any type of joint event not included in clustering activities. - When choosing Other, please specify the activity in the section 'Why'.	Choose the most appropriate target audience from the list. If more target audiences were addressed, please add as many lines as necessary.	Insert a description of the activity, max 200 characters spaces included.	Choose the status of the dissemination activity from the list. For future activities, please mark them as 'Ongoing' and provide more details to ICONS via email when available, it helps us to promote the activity on social networks.	Please include here the estimated number of people you disseminated the project to. This is necessary to monitor the engagement generated by events. This number will be included in the monitoring activity of the project.
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8 Annex 2 – Publications template

Table 41: Publications monitoring table

PUBLICATIONS (scientific papers in journals, conference proceedings etc.).																	
Partner	Type of publication	Type of peer review	PID of deposited publication	Link to publication	Title of the publication	PID of publisher version of record	ISSN/eISSN	Authors	Title of the journal or equivalent	Number	Publisher	Month/Year of publication	PID of book	Book title	Was the publication available in open access through the repository at the time of publication	Did you charge OA publishing fees to the project?	Licence type

9 References

Folco Giuliana, Gaboardi Elena, Lischetti Serena, Martinoli Mario, Mazzolo Giulio, & Schmid Elisabeth. (2022). *Two new tools for science communication assessment: the community engagement index and communication effectiveness quadrants*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6985584>

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